

Title:

How national culture (values, traditions, ethics) and organisational culture (particularly within UBD) shape your perspectives on your future career.

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Abstract

According to Finio and Downie of IBM, organizational development is the idea of planning and creating a systemic process to change the strategies while developing to improve the organizations' performance and growth. This is a reflective essay on how national culture values, traditions, ethics and organisational culture particularly within UBD shape my perspectives on my future career. It will consist of how some criteria affect the perception of future career while including my own views and experience. I have chosen this module to see and learn more on how other students perceive the work culture in Brunei and also learn about their experience in various different industries.

Content

National culture plays an important role in shaping the perspective of a future career. Culture refers to the idea of a group or community way of life that reflects their belief and tradition that plays into the factors shaping the community. National culture refers to how the society adapts the traditions and beliefs of the ancestors with the integration of society that will shape the community to be diverse from other cultures. National culture shapes the perspective of future career by integrating the national culture with work culture while simultaneously adapting with modern technology and society. With this integration, organisations can achieve cultural harmony and local acceptance that differs from foreign organization and culture. Growing up, Bruneian culture has taught me a society that reflects kindness, discipline, great hospitality, honesty, and being a responsible part of society. In addition, I was able to observe these in practice when I went for my internship in college and experienced how the national culture is practiced in the work culture.

Values reflect that an individual has the ability to think and judge based on their principles. The ability to think and judge is considered valuable in the career industry because it shows that the individual is able to judge situations and think of solutions to remedy any issues. In UBD, my way of thinking based on my values and principles have some differences with my peers' values based on their principles and create opportunities to learn on how some people have different approaches to solve problems.

Ethics is the idea of being able to think what is acceptable and permissible to conduct while being able to think what is good for society. This ability is widely emphasised by organizations as they reflect both on the individual character and organizational reputation. In addition, ethics plays a role in shaping trustworthy and honest employees and gaining societal trust for the organization. Ethics is part of what can shape the perspective of a future career. In UBD I am able to learn that different people have different types of ethics based on culture, belief and religion. This also gives me the opportunity to learn that sometimes what we think is good for society is actually harmful and unethical in the working culture.

As stated by Chalmers et al. (2025), organizational culture is the collective belief and expectations by members of the organization on perspective, values and societal norms that shapes the culture. In Universiti Brunei Darussalam (UBD), organizational culture also plays an important role in shaping the perspective of a future career by collectively nurturing students with exposure to diverse cultures and environments. UBD offers students on a program called Discovery Year where students are given the opportunities to study abroad and learn about other cultures through experiences, internships to expose students to the career industry whether abroad or local, volunteering to help better society or creating business ideas that could potentially help students achieve success. This program helps students to collectively change their individual perspective on how to perceive society and different environments.

In conclusion, these factors are what shape and change how I perceive the career industry and the exposure to different cultures and perspectives on how society operates. With meeting people of different ethnicities, cultures and religions and beliefs, it opens the opportunity for me to learn how they think and approach solutions with their own values, beliefs and individual principles. Furthermore, these experiences have changed the way I perceive society by making thought provoking ideas, seeing different sides of arguments and creating an understanding of different cultures that integrate modern values into their career industry. I am striving to understand further about the working culture in Brunei while comparing foreign culture based on my own experience and conversing with people who have the opportunities and sharing that with my peers.

References

Finio.M. & Downie.A.(n.d.). What is organizational development?.*IBM Think*.

<https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/organizational-development>

National Center for Biotechnology Information.(2025). *Organizational culture*. National Library of Medicine.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK560543/>